

SORPTION PROCESS AND IMMERSSED-FATIGUE RESPONSE OF GR/EP COMPOSITES IN SEA WATER

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ABSTRACT

This article presents data of absorption and desorption of pressurized sea water by AS4/3501-6 gr/ep composites. In addition, S-N diagrams are given for the fatigue life of $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_s$ coupons that are cycled in air and under immersed conditions.

Although the sorption data deviate slightly from classical diffusion, the departures can be explained by the viscoelasticity of the polymer and do not portend irreversible damage. On the other hand the extensive fatigue-induced damage introduces capillary flow in coupons that are cycled mechanically while immersed in ambient water. The combined effect of mechanical fatigue and water saturated capillaries causes a substantial reduction of fatigue life, when compared to non-immersed cases.

Both sorption and fatigue data are explained by suitable analytical models.

INTRODUCTION

The effects of moisture and fluids on polymers and polymeric composites have been studied extensively and reviewed periodically over the past several decades. No references will be listed herein for the sake of brevity.

Of major concerns are deleterious effects on material properties attributable to fluids. In many circumstances such degradations are due to the physical/chemical effects of the fluid itself, while in other cases reductions occur when fluids interact with other causes - such as mechanical load.

This article provides an example, which corresponds to graphite/epoxy composites immersed in sea water, of a benign sorption process which turns harmful when coupled with mechanical fatigue. It is worth noting that relatively sparse data are currently available on the combined effect of sorption and fatigue. More significantly, most of those data were obtained for pre-exposed samples which were subsequently fatigued in air. This type of experiment does not represent the immersed circumstance because it discards the very significant effect of capillarity, whose presence will enhance and accelerate the failure process.

SORPTION OF SEA WATER BY GR/EP COMPOSITES

The sorption of fluids by polymeric composites is typified by any one of the five curves shown in Fig. 1. In that fig. the curve "LF" corresponds to the classical, linear Fickian process and serves as a reference^[1], while absorption along curves "A" and "B" can be explained by means of the reversible viscoelastic-like response of the matrix^[2]. The foregoing "benign" circumstances are

contrasted by sorption data along curves "C" or "D", which are associated with irreversible degradation and damage phenomena that are due to chemical or mechanical causes.

The absorption of simulated sea water, pressurized at 0, 2000, and 3000 psi, by a uni-directionally reinforced AS4/3501-6 gr/ep composite was observed to follow curve "A" in Fig. 1 with maximal average values of weight gain of 1.6% at $p = 0$ and 1.8% at $p = 3000$ psi (data scatter is about 0.3%). Typical weight-gain and weight-loss under desorption curves are shown in Fig. 2, with time re-set to zero at onset of desorption. The hysteresis loop in Fig. 2 is commonplace to sorption processes which follow curves "A" or "B" in Fig. 1. Sorption under cyclic pressure is exhibited in Fig. 3, where weight gain data were monitored under weekly pressure cycles between 0 and 3000 psi. The foregoing data fall between the weight-gain curves at constant pressure values of 0 and 3000 psi.

The data shown in Fig. 2 fits curve "A" in Fig. 1 and can be predicted by classical diffusion theory, except that time-dependent boundary conditions should be employed even for constant ambient conditions^[3], namely

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial m}{\partial t} &= D \frac{\partial^2 m}{\partial z^2} & -h \leq z \leq h, \quad t > 0 \\ m(z, 0) &= 0 & -h < z < h \\ m(\pm h, t) &= m_0 + \sum m_i e^{-t/t_i} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

It is therefore apparent that sea water alone is unlikely to degrade gr/ep composites.

SEA WATER COUPLED WITH FATIGUE OF GR/EP COMPOSITES: EXPERIMENTAL OBSERVATIONS

Cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3]_s$ AS4/3501-6 coupons were fatigued at 5Hz frequency at maximal stress levels of 0.74, 0.79, 0.84 and 0.89 σ_{ult} ($\sigma_{ult} = 540$ MPa) with $R = \sigma_{min}/\sigma_{max} = 0.1$. The experiments included dry and pre-saturated specimens fatigued in air and pre-saturated specimens fatigued while immersed in sea water. The resulting S-N curves are shown in Fig. 4.

Note that the fatigue life of the dry coupons is shorter than that of pre-saturated samples fatigued in air, but longer than that of pre-saturated specimens fatigued while immersed in water. Inspection of failed coupons revealed more extensive delaminations and fewer transverse cracks under immersed fatigue when compared with fatigue-in-air. Typical observations are shown in Figs. 5a and 5b.

Additional experiments recorded the rate of capillary climb within the transverse matrix cracks that develop in the 90° ply group under fatigue. X-ray examination of the progression of Di-Iodo Butane (DIB) enhancement fluid indicated that its capillary motion proceeded at a constant velocity of about 1mm per minute. We hypothesize that the capillary motion of sea water occurs at an equivalent speed.

Accordingly, the fatigue response of the specimens investigated herein involves three disparate time scales: (a) diffusion-saturation time $t_s \sim 15 \times 10^4$ min. (b) capillary-climb time across the transverse cracks $t_c \sim 10$ min. (c) fatigue-cycle time $t_f \sim 3 \times 10^{-3}$ min.

The observation that t_c exceeds t_f by four order of magnitudes accounts for the shorter fatigue life under immersion.

STRESS FIELD UNDER "IMMERSED" AND "DRY" FATIGUE: AN APPROXIMATE QUASI-STATIC ANALYSIS.

In view of the foregoing disparity between t_c and t_f it is obvious that sea water which penetrated the fatigue-induced cracks cannot be expelled during the exceedingly short down-loading time intervals of the fatigue cycle. Consequently, during the foregoing time intervals, the nearly incompressible, entrapped sea water exerts pressure on the crack faces, thereby switching a global tension/tension fatigue test into localized tension/compression cyclic stress fields in the vicinities of the above mentioned cracks. Furthermore, the entrapped sea water is squeezed into weakened locations near the transverse crack, most likely into the $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interface, thereby inducing and enhancing delamination growth. The above circumstance occurs in the case of immersed fatigue and is absent otherwise.

An approximate quantitative assessment of the mechanical fields in $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3]_s$ coupons under $\sigma_{max} = 250$ MPa and $\sigma_{min} = 25$ MPa (denoted by σ_M and σ_m in the sequel) under dry, saturated, and saturated-immersed conditions is obtained by means of the shear-lag analysis outlined below^[4].

Consider a coupon of length $2l$, width $2w$ and thickness $2h$. Let the internal, 90° , ply group contain n equally spaced transverse cracks of cross-sectional area $(3/2)wh$ and spacing $2L = 2l/n$.

Due to symmetry it suffices to consider the representative volume $0 \leq x \leq L$, $0 \leq y \leq w$, and $0 \leq z \leq h$, with the transverse crack at $x = L$.

Basic laminate analysis yields the following stress-strain relations^[4]

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(i)} &= Q_{11}^{(i)} (\bar{u}^{(i)'} - \alpha_1^{(i)} \Delta T - \beta_1^{(i)} m) + Q_{12}^{(i)} (\bar{\epsilon}_y - \alpha_2^{(i)} \Delta T - \beta_2^{(i)} m) \\ \bar{\sigma}_y^{(i)} &= Q_{12}^{(i)} (\bar{u}^{(i)'} - \alpha_1^{(i)} \Delta T - \beta_1^{(i)} m) + Q_{22}^{(i)} (\bar{\epsilon}_y - \alpha_2^{(i)} \Delta T - \beta_2^{(i)} m) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In Eqns (2) $Q_{\alpha\beta}$ denote in-plane stiffnesses, α and β are thermal and moisture expansion coefficients, and bars designate averages. The superscript (i) corresponds to the 90° ply group ($i = 1$) and the 0° plies ($i = 2$). In addition, prime denotes derivative with respect to x .

Shear-lag analysis gives the following equilibrium expressions

$$\begin{aligned} -h^{(1)} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)'} &= h^{(2)} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(2)'} = \tau \\ \text{and} \\ h^{(1)} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(1)} + h^{(2)} \bar{\sigma}_x^{(2)} &= (h^{(1)} + h^{(2)}) \bar{\sigma}_{app} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $h^{(i)}$ denotes ply-group thickness, while τ and $\bar{\sigma}_{app}$ are the interlaminar shear stress and applied stress, respectively.

Finally, the assumptions of shear-lag theory yield

$$\tau = A_{55} \left(\frac{\bar{u}^{(2)} - \bar{u}^{(1)}}{h^{(1)} + h^{(2)}} \right) \quad (4)$$

with $A_{55} = 3 (h^{(1)} + h^{(2)}) G_{12} G_{23} / (h^{(1)} G_{23} + h^{(2)} G_{12})$, where G_{12} and G_{23} denote the longitudinal and transverse shear moduli, respectively.

The solution to Eqns (2), (3) and (4) is well documented^[4] and, for the sake of brevity, will not be reproduced here.

The only departure from established results occurs in the computation of stress fields during the down loading stage of mechanical fatigue under immersed condition. In this circumstance the transverse crack at $x = L$ is not traction free and, in view of the assumed incompressibility of sea water, a compressive stress $\sigma_x^{(1)}$ is transmitted without hindrance across the plane $x = L$.

Consequently, the ordinary boundary condition $\sigma_x^{(1)}(L) = 0$ is no longer appropriate in the saturated-immersed circumstance when $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = \bar{\sigma}_0 < \sigma_M$. In that circumstance, the stress field is obtained by superposition of the shear-lag solution due to $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = \sigma_M$ (with moisture m and temperature excursion ΔT) and the laminated plate solution for an unfractured coupon subjected to $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = -(\sigma_M - \bar{\sigma}_0)$ (with $m = 0$ and $\Delta T = 0$). The computational results exhibited below correspond to $\bar{\sigma}_0 = \sigma_m = 25$ MPa.

The computations assumed the following values: $Q_{11} = 139.8$, $Q_{12} = 3.0$, $Q_{22} = 11.06$, $G_{12} = 4.8$ and $G_{23} = 5.5$ (all in GPa), $\alpha_1 = 0.9 \times 10^{-6}$, $\alpha_2 = 31 \times 10^{-6}$ (in $m/m/1^\circ C$), $\beta_1 = 0.01 \times 10^{-2}$, $\beta_2 = 0.32 \times 10^{-2}$ (in $m/m/1\%$ weight-gain), $\Delta T = -125^\circ C$, $m = 1.7\%$, ply thickness $h_0 = 0.125$ and crack spacing $2L = 2.0$ (both in mm).

Results are shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig. 6 exhibits the stress $\sigma_x^{(90)}$ vs. x under $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = \sigma_M = 250$ MPa and $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = \sigma_m = 25$ MPa, respectively, in the dry ($m = 0$) and saturated ($m = 1.7\%$) cases. All plots include residual thermal stresses due to $\Delta T = -125^\circ C$ and correspond to the non immersed case. Note the beneficial effect of m , which counters the effect of $(-\Delta T)$.

Figure 7 shows the stress $\sigma_x^{(90)}$ vs. x under $\bar{\sigma}_{app} = \sigma_m$ in the immersed case. Note that in contrast with Figs. 6a and 6b, in this case $\sigma_x^{(90)}(x = L = 1.0 \text{ mm}) \neq 0$, with compressive stresses in the range between $x \sim 0.4$ mm and $x = 1.0$ mm.

Though delamination analysis is beyond the scope of the present shear-lag model, the compression-induced injection of sea water into the interlaminar regions adjacent to $L = 1.0$ would result in the extensive delaminations observed in Fig. 5a.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that an inherently benign diffusion process can enhance the damage process of polymeric composites when coupled with mechanical fatigue. The coupling becomes especially significant when fatigue occurs under immersed conditions, in view of the critical significance of capillary action which exists in that circumstance.

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FIGURES

Fig. 1 Schematic curves representing four categories of recorded non-fickian weight-gain sorption data in polymers and polymeric composites. The solid line, designated by LF, corresponds to linear Fickian diffusion. Curves "C" and "D" are associated with irreversible material degradations.

Fig. 2 Absorption of sea water at pressure of 3000 psi and its desorption in air vs. $\sqrt{\text{time}}$. Time was re-set at $t = 0$ for desorption data.

Fig. 3 Variation in sea water weight gain due to weekly pressure fluctuations between 0 and 3000 psi.

Fig. 4 S - N data for $[0/90_3]_s$ AS4/3501-6 coupons (——— dry coupons fatigued in air, ····· saturated coupons fatigued while immersed, - - - - - saturated coupons fatigued in air).

(a) pre-saturated immersed

(b) dry

Fig. 5 Failed $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ gr/ep fatigued specimens.

Fig. 6 σ_x^{90} vs. x for the dry case, $\sigma_{app}^{max} = 250$ MPa \blacklozenge — \blacklozenge , and $\sigma_{app}^{min} = 25$ MPa \blacksquare --- \blacksquare , and for the immersed case at $\sigma_{app}^{max} = 250$ MPa \square — \square .

Fig. 7 σ_x^{90} vs. x for the immersed case at $\sigma_{app}^{min} = 25$ MPa. Note the extensive compressive region adjacent to the crack located at $x = 1$.